

RES4CITY CASE STUDY #3

Methodology to estimate **Decarbonisation** potential at the neighborhood level

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Executive Summary

Figure 5. Summary of the Project Methodology

The main objective of this case study is to quantify GHG emissions across sectors Figure 5 in the Benicalap district of Valencia in order to create a roadmap for the integration of renewable energy and the eventual achievement of carbon neutrality in the district.

Through this analysis, it was possible to conclude that nature-based solutions (NBS), photovoltaic production, sustainable transport and efficiency in public lighting are the best strategies for a successful energy transition.

Abstract

The Benicalap district is located on the outskirts of Valencia; it is among the city's top 6 most densely populated districts. It is mainly residential, with relatively old buildings and good public transport connections. However, private vehicle transit is also highly relevant. On top of that, Benicalap is expected to host a vital venue: the new football stadium, with the corresponding increase in transit, emissions, and services.

However, according to the City Hall, 12.465 neighbours are in a state of "vulnerability"; most of

the population (69% of workers) are occupied in the service sector, and the unemployment rate is 34%. Thus, the energy transition in this district will accomplish an ambitious technical challenge while coping with a vulnerable population immersed in an expanding tertiary economy. Therefore, considerations of fairness and social innovation are mandatory for this project (Ajuntament de València, 2023).

The urban energy transition proposed for this district is a

disruptive solution through district-based integration of renewable energy sources. The primary district resource is its solar potential of around 1.650 kWh/kWp. The strategy contemplates some actions: deployment of local energy communities, use of nature-based solutions, buildings' retrofitting programs, and transportation electrification. The impact of the solutions is measured regarding their energy savings and emission factors (European Commission, 2022c).

This case study shows how to exploit all the resources available in a district to accomplish a fair energy transition and to make them work together. Pilot experiences like this are essential to standardize processes and accelerate them.

This project aims to develop a methodology to estimate the decarbonization potential at a neighbourhood level and the road map to achieve the decarbonization goals in the neighbourhood of Benicalap.

To carry out the methodology, state-of-the-art is elaborated, based on the information obtained, an emissions inventory is worked on, and these emissions are quantified. The emissions inventory is carried out by analyzing sectors such as energy, transport, land use, and others. Subsequently, lines of action are proposed with their respective measures for neutralizing these emissions in the different sectors, developed and analyzed from a technical, economic, environmental, and social perspective (Roncero Tarazona, 2023; van den Dobbelsteen et al., 2018).

Once the lines of action are developed, an emissions balance is drawn up, evaluating the contribution that each of the focal points of action makes to the decarbonization of the neighbourhood, assessing whether it is possible to achieve the objective of neighbourhoods with zero emissions, or if not, including future guidelines to achieve it.

Introduction

Human-induced climate change has caused widespread adverse impacts and related losses and damages to nature and people.” That is the first conclusion of the sixth assessment report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC): Impacts, Adaptation, and Vulnerability. Hence, experts report that the accelerated change we are witnessing

becomes an impossible problem to avoid. We must focus on reducing their impacts and stopping the current trend. In this context, cities are crucial as they cause 70% of emissions worldwide.

In addition, high population density in cities produces enormous social and economic impacts. Therefore, transforming cities and generating more sustainable urban ecosystems is both a challenge and an opportunity. It is necessary to develop strategies that reduce these impacts and consider the various factors involved in the sustainability of cities to achieve carbon-neutral cities (IPCC, 2023; United Nations, 2023).

A literature review is done to obtain a clear view of the work. On the one hand, a carbon footprint review highlights the methods and the general results for cities. On the other hand, a review of the leading carbon reduction strategies in cities and their connection with the different aspects of ecosystems in cities.

In the last few years, the European Union has been working hard on the GHG inventory, scope, data collection, footprint calculations, interpreting the results, and proposing and planning mitigation and reduction plans (IEA, 2021; Ministerio para la Transición Ecológica y el Reto Demográfico, 2023).

In terms of mitigation plans, much has been done in Scope 1 and Scope 2, which corresponds to direct emissions and indirect emissions through the generation of emissions, respectively. However, little has been said about mitigation actions for indirect emissions resulting from people's activities, scope 3. One of the reasons is that they are the most difficult to quantify in detail and are directly related to citizens' consumption habits (Fong et al., 2021; Ghaemi & Smith, 2020; Shan et al., 2018).

This project aims to develop a methodology to estimate

the decarbonization potential at a neighbourhood level and the road map to achieve the decarbonization goals in the neighbourhood of Benicalap in Valencia City (Wieselblad, 2021).

This research study's specific main goals are:

- Develop a GHG emissions inventory considering the different activity sectors.
- Build a methodology to estimate and analyze the decarbonization potential in specific city zones.
- Search for and propose measures to reduce GHG emissions and quantify the impact of each step on the initial GHG inventory to analyze the final situation.
- Realise a carbon balance by years, considering the actions proposed.
- Analyse and detail future actions and directions to follow to improve and complete the carried-out study.

- Analyse and detail a methodology to determine the principal components of the scope three emissions inventory.
- Propose and analyse some mitigation plans for scope 3.

Several tools have been used to achieve a relevant, complete, consistent, transparent, and accurate methodology.

Some of them are:

- QGIS: This tool has been used to estimate the building surface available to implement solar photovoltaic (PV) installations on the rooftops of the buildings.
- Datadis: This online platform has been used to obtain the daily and hourly electricity consumption values in the different neighbourhoods.
- PVGIS: (Photovoltaic Geographical Information

System) is an online tool developed by JRC (Joint Research Centre) of Ispra (Italia) from the European Commission, which has a database about solar resources.

- HOMER: (Hybrid Optimization Model for Multiple Energy Resources) is a software developed by the National Renewable Energy Laboratory and improved and distributed by Homer Energy. It has been used to dimension and evaluate the neighbourhood's photovoltaic potential as one measure to try to reduce emissions associated with electricity consumption.
- EXCEL: Organise, combine, and analyse information. Likewise, to make projections, graphs, and scenarios.

Based on the initial GHG inventory, four measures have been proposed for the decarbonization of the neighbourhood: NBS, PV generation, sustainable transport, and efficiency in public lighting. Having developed all these measures, PV generation is the highest contributor to CO₂ emissions, followed by the measures proposed for transport. The electrification of vehicles reduces around 3% of the total initial emissions. The other two measures have a low impact on the total emissions, with a less than 1% reduction contribution.

As mentioned above, conducting a more in-depth investigation into the measurement and mitigation plans for Scope 3, corresponding mainly to the consumption of goods and services, is essential.

Description of Case Study

Develop a methodology to estimate the decarbonization potential at the neighbourhood level and the road map to achieve it in a specific neighbourhood of the city of Valencia: Benicalap—one of the city's most important and dense neighbourhoods.

The specific steps to achieve the objective of this case study are:

- Develop a GHG emissions inventory considering the different activity sectors in the neighbourhoods.
- Build a methodology to estimate and analyze the decarbonization potential in specific city zones, the neighbourhoods.
- Search for and propose measures to reduce GHG emissions and quantify the impact of each measure on

the initial GHG inventory to analyse the final situation.

- Realise a carbon balance by years, considering the actions proposed.
- Analyse and detail future actions and directions to follow to improve and complete the carried-out study.

Benicalap is one of the 87 neighbourhoods of Valencia; it is located in the north and is part of one of the 19 districts named in the same way (Ajuntament de l'Hospitalet, 2017).

It is among the top 6 most densely populated districts of the city. It is mainly residential, with relatively old buildings and good public transport connections. However, since it is in the outskirts, private vehicle transit through Benicalap is also highly relevant.

- Has 41.483 habitants; 1,72 km² of area; and density of population of 24.132.
- The majority of the population is between 30 and 50 years of age and are professionals.
- There are 18.968 buildings, most built between 1961 and 1980.
- Energy consumption is 77.085,33 MWh, of which 59% corresponds to the residential sector, 29% for the service sector, and 2% for the industry.
- The initial GHG inventory determines the total annual emissions are 18.4379, of which 66% corresponds to the consumption of goods, followed by transportation (18%), electricity (7%) and natural gas consumption (5%).

Case Study Solution

Figure 5 details the methodology and process used for this project. The first step is defining the project and the planned objectives to achieve during the study. To determine the main project scope and objectives, it is important to plan some questions to bear in mind to define it, such as *“What do carbon neutrality plans in your*

city focus on? What does carbon neutrality mean for your city? What real benefits do you see for your city in implementing these plans? What are the main stakeholder groups the city needs to engage to implement those plans?

Having defined the project and the lines to follow, a detailed review of the state-of-the-art in different topics related to carbon neutrality was carried out. The documents included and reviewed in this step were of various types, research articles, check articles, government documents related to studies, statistics from the Valencia City Council or the Valencian Community, and reports from the European Community or other institutions (Ministerio para la Transición Ecológica y el Reto Demográfico, 2023).

Based on that, a good concept of carbon neutrality application in the cities was constructed. The main topics searched include carbon neutrality, sustainable cities, energy

efficiency in buildings, natural-based solutions, circular economy, involving stakeholders in programs, PV generation on rooftops, etc.

With the information obtained from the elaboration of the state-of-the-art and the concepts clear, the next step is to analyse the initial situation of the place where the project will be applied. In the case of this specific study, a set of initial information was gathered and evaluated:

- Main characteristics of the neighbourhood: total surface, use of the land, population, and characteristics of the population (age, gender, job, etc.), transport system, green areas, and other data that, with the progress of the study, has been considered important and useful.
- In some cases, a visit to the neighbourhood was executed to understand the characteristics and evaluate the data collected from the different sources.

- Energy consumption is divided into residential, industrial, and services sectors.
- GHG inventory by sectors. Obtain data from the characteristics of the sectors in the neighbourhood, the emissions per type of sector, and other aspects of developing this inventory.
- The transport system in the neighbourhood.

Considering the initial situation of the neighbourhood and using the concepts extracted from the development of the state-of-the-art related to the possible measures to reduce CO₂ emissions, a list of measures has been proposed to make a multilevel analysis of the economic, technical, social, and environmental impact on the initial situation.

The summary of the list of measures is as follows:

- Renewable generation based on PV generation.

- Evolution of the transport fleet for private and public transport to sustainable transport.
- Implementation of natural-based solutions.
- Energy efficiency measures in public lighting.

Considering the proposed measures is necessary to analyse the impact and contribution to the CO₂ reduction of the initial situation that each measure can produce. In that way, it will be possible to concrete which measure has a more significant impact as it is more important to develop, not only considering the CO₂ reduction, the economic impact, the social affection, etc. And with all these data priorities the different measures in a temporal line.

With the previous results obtained from the simulation of the proposed measures, the sensitivity analysis for this study has been carried out. In

this case, the variables or aspects considered changeable in this analysis and that have been included as important to evaluate the impact of this change in the project has been:

- Energy price.
- Increase in consumption.
- Increase of electric vehicles.

One of the main reasons for this study is to evaluate the impact of different measures proposed in the literature to achieve carbon neutrality in cities. For this, a CO₂ balance has been carried out. Starting from the initial situation and considering a curve estimated for the CO₂ emissions during the following years and considering the CO₂ reduction based on the proposed measures, a CO₂ balance has been presented in this document for the following years until 2030 (Furió et al., 2019).

In this work, the GHG Inventory has been developed by dividing all the emissions emitted today

into diverse groups to calculate this in detail. The groups which are included in this document are buildings (electricity and gas consumption), transport, consumption of goods, waste, and public lighting.

A. Buildings

To estimate the emissions coming from the operation of the different buildings, the information on the total consumption of electricity and gas for the city of Valencia has been used. After that, this data was extrapolated according to the habitants of Benicalap.

B. Transport

To calculate the emissions generated by the different means of transport, transport has been divided into two groups: private transport and public transport.

To determine the current situation of private transport in Valencia and, more specifically, in Benicalap, the personal vehicles will be small trucks, passenger cars, two-wheelers, and bicycles.

First, the number of each type of private transport in Valencia was obtained from Dirección General de Tráfico (DGT) to evaluate the emissions. These vehicles are calculated based on the European Regulation that groups the vehicles in various groups depending on the year of matriculation (DGT, 2023).

Based on that regulation, the data used to calculate the emissions has been:

- Total of each mean of transport vehicles grouped due to the regulation in each neighbourhood.
- Total kilometres travelled for each vehicle depending on the type and year.
- Emissions per kilometre depending on the type and year of the vehicle.

Another emission that should be considered due to the use of private transport is the ones coming from the vehicles that are not considered private vehicles in the neighbourhood

but pass through it and emit GHG in the area.

These emissions have been calculated using the IMD (Intensidad Media Diaria de Vehículos) available for the main streets in Valencia, the kilometer of each one of these avenues, and the general emissions per kilometer considered for this calculation.

On the other hand, the public transport of the city of Valencia comprises four main means of transportation: seven metro lines, four tram lines, a wide range of bus lines that will be detailed, and Valenbisi service, which is the bicycle-sharing service.

In the case of Benicalap, there is a metro, bus, and tram system. The activity of the public transport bus is calculated considering the distance of each line that passes through the neighbourhood, the number of trips performed per type of day, weekday, weekend, and holiday and the emissions related to each means of transport.

On the other hand, there is the bicycle sharing service; in the city of Valencia, there are a total of 2.750 bicycles, divided into 277 stations in all the city and 5.502 locking points. Based on the map of all the stations in the city, the bicycles in Benicalap are 66.

C. Consumption of goods

The consumption of goods in society nowadays is very remarkable because it could be qualified as consumerist, and the purchase and use of a higher number of necessary goods, supposes an increment in the CO₂ emissions related to these processes that could be reduced by implementing good practices in the consumption of goods. The goods considered in this inventory are food, clothes, and other manufactured products like furniture and technology devices.

The previous inventory of food consumption is based on the “Informe del Consumo de Alimentación en España

2020” where a total of 27 food categories were estimated for Spanish society consumption. To calculate the emissions produced by this consumption is necessary to consider the CO2 emission factors for each previous item included (Ministerio de Agricultura, 2020)

Combining the previous values, the CO2 emissions per capita have been calculated and detailed.

How it was mentioned before, this is one of the points related to scope 3, and it is one of the most important in terms of consumption and emission relevance. Also, it is one of the points that are more difficult to calculate and generally is a gap in this kind of project.

This is one of the main motivations to deepen this project and type of research and thus to create a methodology that facilitates and reduces the uncertainty of this scope and, in turn, allows to evaluate of different mitigation options and plans in the changes in consumption of the inhabitants.

D. Waste

Other emissions that have been considered in this inventory are related to the generation and management of waste. First, the total waste generation in the neighbourhood per waste type (Municipal solid waste, organic, glass, paper, plastic, vegetable oil, and batteries) and then scaled to the neighbourhood using the downscaling factors.

After that, it is necessary to divide the waste type into management categories. In this case, the categories considered has haven landfilling, recycling, energy generation,n, and composting. It is important to consider the emissions that are included in each of the waste management categories:

- Recycling: includes transport to a recycling facility and sorting of recycled materials at a material recovery facility.

- Landfilling: includes transport to landfill, the equipment used at the landfill, and fugitive landfill CH₄ emissions. Landfill CH₄ is based on typical landfill gas collection practices and average landfill moisture conditions.
- Composition: include transport to a composting facility, the equipment uses at the composting facility, and CH₄ and N₂O emissions during composting.

E. Public lighting

The public lighting installed in streets, gardens, parks, monuments, and other public elements are responsible for a part of the CO₂ emissions from the neighbourhood.

Based on the statistic of the Valencia City Hall, the total consumption of electricity from public lighting is known. To adapt these values of the district to the selected neighbourhood, the downscaling factors for Benicalap have been considered; in this case, the

factors used and being more adequate due to the type of distribution of public lighting have been the area.

Having developed the GHG inventory of the current emissions, the next step of this project is to propose different measures to reduce carbon emissions and approach carbon neutrality. Some of the proposes are:

F. Natural Based Solutions

First, it is necessary to expose what Natural Based Solutions (NBS) are. There are means of bringing nature back into cities, following the example of natural ecosystems and achieving environmental, social, and economic benefits to improve urban sustainability.

Another aspect to consider in the analysis of natural solutions is the type of urban areas in which the project is proposed. Different zones are grouped into classes depending on a variety of

characteristics such as land use, the type of buildings, etc. The urban zones are classified as urban zones with high density, urban zones with low density, urban zones of community equipment, and new development urban zones. Considering the characteristics of Benicalap, it can be regarded as an urban zone with high density that has a high surface occupied by buildings and a low surface with vegetal zones, been in the majority alone trees or small garden. The recommendation in a wide range of studies is to increase the vegetation in buildings, focusing on court blocks, terraces, roofs, and facades. In the case of Benicalap, an area in the north of the neighbourhood can be included in the group of urban zones with low density because the size of green zones is larger than in the rest. And the plan in this area is to increase the density of the current green zones with autochthonous species, apart from creating new green zones in accessible spaces.

To propose a solution based on natural solutions, it is necessary to determine the base and current situation of this solution in the neighbourhoods. Using the Geoportal of the city of Valencia, there is one section with information about the green zones in the city of Valencia, including the name of the green zone, the neighbourhood to which it belongs, and the surface in square meters. Working with this data, it is possible to calculate the total green zone area of the neighbourhood.

In the case of Benicalap, there are 39 green zones in all the areas, including parks, gardens, green zones on sidewalks, etc. The total area that covers these zones is 135.228 m², representing 7,87 % of the entire surface of the neighbourhood.

G. PV generation

PV systems on the neighbourhoods' roofs have been proposed as one measure to decarbonize the city's electricity consumption.

The energy generated by the potential PV installations has been calculated using the software Homer.

Plenty of simulations have been developed, considering different percentages of the functional area and different inclinations. After this first filter, the final selection has been based on the higher production of photovoltaic energy and comparing the payback between the options.

H. Sustainable transport

One of the main sectors responsible for GHG emissions in the neighbourhoods is the transport sector, and more precisely, the private and commercial transport,

including the measures in public transport. Therefore, the basis on that and the necessity to reduce these emissions, a series of measures will be proposed based on the “Plan de Movilidad Urbana Sostenible” of Valencia (Ajuntament de València, 2013).

One of these objectives that will be presented and developed are:

- Apply measures with the objective of the decarbonization of the transport system.
- Enhance the pedestrian’s movements when the distance allows it.
- Increase the cycle paths and the number of public bicycles available to promote cycle movements.
- Promote public transport instead of private transport, with the analysis of the current system and the potential of zones with the worst connections.

- Promote the increase of electric vehicles both in public and private transport.
- Increase the use of electric cars.
- Increase the participation of hybrids and electrical buses.

H. Public lighting

Another planned measure is related to public lighting, a straightforward measure that the Ayuntamiento de Valencia can develop to reduce emissions.

The current situation of public lighting in different spaces, such as parks, streets, etc., is based on a wide range of lighting, mainly: high-pressure sodium led, LED lights, metal halogen lights, and others less frequent.

One of the measures that the city of Valencia is planning is substituting the luminaries for others more efficiently to reduce the consumption of public lighting and, consequently, CO2 emissions.

Also, flux reducers and astronomic clocks will help reduce electricity consumption. Subsequently, a detailed technical analysis is performed. A social and economic analysis follows this to determine a roadmap of the actions and the estimated reduction percentages.

Results and Discussion

With all the information mentioned above and following the methodology explained. The following preliminary results are obtained regarding the emissions inventory (Figure 6).

In the project's first phase, approximate emissions for the neighbourhood of 184,380 tons of CO₂/year were determined. Of these, 77% of the emissions correspond to Scope 3, 66.39% being due to the consumption of goods, especially food and clothing. This is followed by

private transportation emissions, which account for 18% of total emissions with 33,128 Tons of CO₂/year.

This was followed by electricity consumption in the residential, services, and industrial sectors, totalling 13,259 tons of CO₂ equivalent and corresponding to 7.2% of total emissions. Next is the consumption of natural gas, especially for the residential sector, with a 4.87% share.

Figure 6. GHG Inventory Benicalap Valencia

GHG Inventory (OPEX):

The project's initial phase aims to analyze scopes 1 and 2 in more detail, so these results will be further explored. After a detailed technical analysis and considering each proposed initiative's social, environmental, and economic considerations, a proposed scenario and a road map for its implementation are given.

Figure 7. Comparison with the initial and proposed situation

Results for BENICALAP

**Initial
CO2**

**SCOPES
1&2**

42399 tCO2/year

Percentage of CO2 savings			
Year	2020	2025	2030
NBS	0.051%	0.082%	0.152%
PV Generation	0.0%	14.53%	24.87%
Public Lighting	0.0%	0.15%	0.28%
Sustainable Trasnport	0.0%	12.7%	25.39%
Total	0.051%	27.46%	50.69%

**Final
CO2**

**SCOPES
1&2**

22515 tCO2/year

An estimate is made of the achievable achievements in reducing emissions of these Scopes due to each of the mitigation proposals, where self-generation and a more sustainable transportation model are the most relevant measures, achieving a 50% reduction of emissions by 2030 and starting from 42.399 TonCO₂ year and reaching 22.515 TonCO₂ year. In the mitigation proposals, and as mentioned above, the change of public lighting and the creation of green spaces are also considered.

Figure 8 shows the proposed road map for each mitigation measure in more detail.

Natural-Based Solutions

Nowadays, green area spaces represent 7,87% of the area of the Neighborhood. The recommendation in a wide range of studies, such as (Gutiérrez et al., 2016), in these zones is to increase the vegetation in buildings, focusing on court blocks, terraces, roofs, and facades. The plan is to increase the density of the

existing areas and create new green zones in free spaces, with a proposed execution of 40% of the scope by 2025 and 100% by 2030.

Public lighting

The current situation of public lighting in different spaces, such as parks, streets, etc., is based on a wide range of lighting, mainly: high-pressure sodium led, LED lights, metal halogen lights, and others less frequent. The recommendation is to make the changeover so that all public lighting is LED technology.

Sustainable transport

A series of measures are proposed for the transport sector based on the "Plan de Movilidad Urbana Sostenible" (Ajuntament de València, 2013). The diagram shows in more detail the implementation percentage for each measure from 2022 to 2030:

- Implement measures with the objective of

decarbonisation of the transport system.

- Promote pedestrian travel when distance permits.
- Increase bike lanes and the number of public bicycles available to encourage bicycle commuting.
- Promote public transport instead of private transport by analyzing the current system and the potential of the worst connected areas.
- Promote the increase of electric vehicles in both public and private transport.

Photovoltaic

This proposal consists of installing self-consumption photovoltaic systems on the roofs of buildings. Using Homer, PVGIS, and Google Earth software. It is determined to install 50% of the power calculated for the year 2025 and reach 100% of this, with a total value of 49,000 kW in 2030.

Throughout the project period, it is proposed to carry out awareness campaigns to involve and provide greater knowledge to the community about the responsible use of energy, recycling, the importance of proximity consumption and other elements that seek a change in the habits of people in favor of sustainability.

Figure 8. Roadmap of the proposals

If it is wanted to comply with the agreed-upon environmental commitments, working on this type of project is essential. A clear methodology to determine emissions and abatement potentials will allow us to focus mitigation efforts on the sectors that generate the most significant impact.

Likewise, this type of project can be scalable and replicable, which encourages us to

continue working on them and begin to generate a cascading effect.

Finally, it is essential to understand that this type of new proposed project, in this case, the development of a carbon-neutral neighbourhood, is not only a work that concerns the technical part to achieve it but different non-technical factors should be analysed. It is a new concept that implies a change in

a huge aspect of life that today is planned in a direction that all these new projects will modify.

The main non-technical factors that will be evaluated and modified to adapt to the new conditions are policy, legal, social, and economic factors.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The world and mainly the cities, should change the urban areas to mitigate the effects and adapt to climate change challenges.

Sustainable plans, new policies, actions, and projects or initiatives like the one presented in this document can play a fundamental role in helping cities and governments hit different points and solve these problems, considering the results obtained in these studies (European Commission, 2023; Gronkiewicz-Waltz et al., 2020).

In this project, one methodology to estimate the decarbonization potential was developed to create a roadmap to achieve the planned situation and approach to carbon neutrality.

The GHG emissions inventory was developed for both neighbourhoods, and it is remarkable to say that the

majority of data available is not specific to communities and is accessible at the city level or even at the country level. This lack of data supposes an error in the calculation that, probably in the future, with more precise information, can reduce and have more realistic results.

Apart from the previous indications, the values obtained in this inventory show that the consumption of goods is the highest responsible for emissions. The third scope in some studies is not considered is the more emitted part of the mix. For this, it is important to consider this scope in the analysis. Following this sector, private transport is the second sector with more considerable emissions, and electricity consumption is the third one, with a vast difference from the rest of the sectors, with a minority representation.

Based on the initial GHG inventory, four measures have been proposed for decarbonizing the neighborhoods: NBS, PV generation, sustainable transport, and efficiency in public lighting. Having developed all these measures, PV generation is the highest contributor to CO2 emissions, followed by the measures proposed for transport.

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